

Supramolecular fullerene/porphyrin interaction in solution : spectroscopic and theoretical investigations

Partha Mukherjee and Sumanta Bhattacharya*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Golapbag, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : sum_9974@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-342-2530452

Manuscript received 05 October 2010, accepted 30 December 2010

Abstract : The present paper deals with the study of supramolecular interaction of an octaethyl Zn^{II} porphyrin molecule (1) with C₆₀ and C₇₀ in toluene medium by means of absorption spectrophotometric and luminescence measurements. Stoichiometry of both the fullerene complexes of 1 is determined to be 1 : 1. Binding affinity of 1 towards C₆₀ and C₇₀ is examined by both UV-Vis spectrophotometric and steady state fluorescence spectroscopic techniques, which reveals relatively large value of binding constant (*K*) for the C₇₀/1 system (~23350 dm³ mol⁻¹) in comparison to C₆₀/1 system (i.e. ~11455 dm³ mol⁻¹). Quantum chemical calculations at molecular mechanics level offer insight into the geometric structure of the supramolecules and give formidable support in favour of large value of *K* for the C₇₀/1 system in terms of the heat of formation value of the fullerene/1 complexes.

Keywords : C₆₀ and C₇₀, octaethylporphyrin, UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopic investigations, binding constants, MMMF calculations.

Introduction

There is an increasing interest among the chemists in finding the cooperative effect in non-covalent interactions¹, which can be successfully employed for the construction of quite complex structures². Several classes of porphyrins and derivatized porphyrins³ have been used for this purpose and in many case, the resulting systems are served as models for the study of photo-induced energy^{4,5} and electron transfer^{6,7} processes which mimic events occurring in natural photosynthesis. On the other hand, fullerenes may be employed as attractive building blocks for the construction of supramolecular assemblies and new advanced materials in the light of their unusual electrochemical and electronic properties⁸⁻¹². It is already reported that fullerene and porphyrin form naturally assembled co-crystallates¹³ which are characterized by an unusually short fullerene/porphyrin distance (3.0-3.5)¹⁴, and that a number of fullerene/porphyrin systems form an emissive charge transfer (CT) state both in solutions^{15,16} and in solid state¹⁷. The generality of fullerene/porphyrin attraction is already studied in detail with mesotetraphenylporphyrin¹⁸ and tetrahexylporphyrin^{19,20} from our labs. In continuation of our efforts to investigate fullerene containing host-guest assemblies, we have introduced a new metalloporphyrin, 1 (Fig. 1), as a designed host molecule

Fig. Structure of 1.

in our present investigations. We anticipate, although the four octaethyl groups would not directly involve in the fullerene/porphyrin interaction, they result in a deeper and more rigid cavities with an improved complementarities to the fullerene surface. This is likely to make an impart in the enhanced selectivity between C₆₀ and C₇₀.

In this context, it is very much essential to see the binding affinity of this particular Zn^{II} monoporphyrin with fullerenes C₆₀ and C₇₀ in solution. In our present investigations, we report detailed results of UV-Vis, steady state and time resolved fluorescence spectroscopic measurements to see the interaction between fullerenes (C₆₀ and C₇₀) and **1** in toluene medium. The spectroscopic investigations of the complexes enable us to determine the extent of binding as well as selectivity in binding constant (*K*) between C₆₀/**1** and C₇₀/**1** complexes. Molecular mechanics calculations by force field method (MMMF) have provided very good support for the interpretation of the stability difference between C₆₀ and C₇₀ complexes of **1**.

Experimental

C₆₀ and C₇₀ have been collected from Aldrich, USA. **1** is purchased from Aldrich, USA. Toluene (spectroscopic grade, Merck) is used as solvent, because it is sufficiently apolar to favor non-covalent interaction between fullerene and porphyrin and at the same time, ensures very good solubility and photo-stability of the samples. UV-Vis spectral measurements are performed on a Shimadzu UV-2450 spectrophotometer using quartz cell with 1 cm optical path length. Steady state fluorescence spectral measurements have been recorded in a Hitachi F-4500 fluorescence spectrophotometer. Fluores-

cence decay curves are measured with a HORIBA Jobin Yvon Single Photon Counting Set up employing nanoled as excitation source. Theoretical calculations are done using SPARTAN'06 software.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis investigations :

The ground state absorption spectrum of **1** displays (i) very intense Soret absorption band ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 405 \text{ nm}$) corresponding to the transition to the second excited singlet state S₂ and (ii) two Q bands at 532 and 569 nm corresponding to the vibronic sequence of the transition to the lowest excited single state S₁. Generally in case of metaloporphyrin, the appearance of Soret and Q absorption bands arise from configuration interaction of four orbitals, the nearly degenerate pair a_{1u}, a_{2u}, highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the doubly degenerate e_{1g}, lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), respectively²¹. Ground state electronic interaction between fullerenes and **1** is first evidenced from UV-Vis titration experiment. It is observed that gradual addition of a C₆₀ solution to a toluene solution of **1** decrease the absorbance of Soret band and red shifted it from 405 to 406 nm (Fig. 2). However, no additional absorption peak is observed in the visible region. The former observation extends a very good support in favour of the complex-

Fig. 2. (i) UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** ($5.430 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) recorded against the solvent as reference and set (ii)-(vi) indicates UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** ($5.430 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in the presence of C₆₀ (9.920×10^{-6} to $3.640 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) recorded against the pristine C₆₀ solution as reference.

ation between C_{60} and **1** in ground state. The later observation indicates that the interaction is not controlled by charge transfer (CT) type transition. Similar sort of absorption spectral phenomenon is also observed for C_{70} /**1** system (Fig. 1S) though the Soret absorption band is red shifted by 3 nm probably due to greater interaction between C_{70} and **1** compared to C_{60} . All of the above

1 cm optical path length as shown below.

$$[A]_0[D]_0/d' = ([D]_0/d') + (1/K\epsilon') \quad (1)$$

Here $[A]_0$ and $[D]_0$ are the initial concentrations of the acceptor (i.e. fullerenes C_{60} and C_{70}) and donor (**1**) solutions in toluene, respectively; d' is the corrected absorbance of the fullerene/**1** mixture at the wavelength of

Fig. 1S. UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** ($5.430 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) recorded against the solvent as reference and set (ii)-(vi) indicates UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** ($5.430 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in the presence of C_{70} (3.570×10^{-6} to $4.320 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) recorded against the pristine C_{70} solution as reference.

phenomena indicate that **1** undergoes appreciable interaction with both C_{60} and C_{70} . The most important observation in the present investigation is that the Soret absorption bands get affected more than the Q-absorption bands, which is already observed by Guldi *et al.*²² in their particular fullerene/porphyrin systems. The stoichiometry of the fullerene/**1** complexes is determined by Jobs continuation variation experiment, which indicates that fullerene forms 1 : 1 complex with **1**. Typical Jobs plot for C_{60} /**1** and C_{70} /**1** systems are demonstrated in Figs. 2S and 3, respectively. The gradual decrease in the absorbance of the Soret band of **1** in presence of fullerenes, viz. C_{60} and C_{70} , is used to determine the value of K using well known Benesi-Hildebrand (BH) equation²³ for cells with

Fig. 2S. Jobs plot of continuous variation for C_{60} /**1** system.

Fig. 3. Jobs plot of continuous variation for C₇₀/1 system.

measurement (i.e. 405 nm) recorded against the same porphyrin concentration as reference. The quantity ϵ' means the corrected molar absorptivity of the complex. K is the binding constant of the fullerene/1 complex. Eq. (1) is valid under 1 : 1 approximation for 1 and fullerene systems. It should be mentioned at this point that the corrected molar extinction coefficient, ϵ' , is not quite that of the complex. The BH method²³ is an approximation that we have used many times and it gives decent answers. But the extinction coefficient is really a different one between the complex and free species that absorbs at the same wavelength. Excellent linear BH plots are obtained for both the systems studied in present investigations. Typical BH plots for the C₆₀/1 and C₇₀/1 systems are shown in Figs. 4 and 3S, respectively. Values of K are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 4. BH plot of C₆₀/1 system in toluene at 298 K.

Fig. 3S. BH plot for C₇₀/1 system.

Steady state fluorescence studies :

The binding of fullerenes with 1 has also been accompanied by the steady state fluorescence quenching experiment of 1 in presence of C₆₀ and C₇₀. The fluorescence emission spectral change of 1 upon addition of C₆₀ and C₇₀ are shown in Figs. 5 and 4S, respectively. The titration is performed at a constant concentration of 1. Upon excitation at Soret absorption band, 1 gives two emission bands at 573 and 625 nm. With increase in concentration of fullerene, the intensity of the emission band diminishes gradually. This indicates that there is a relaxation pathway from the excited singlet state of the porphyrin to that of the fullerene in toluene. It is already reported that charge separation could also occur from the excited singlet state of the porphyrin to the C₆₀ in toluene medium²⁴. Competing between the energy and electron transfer processes is a universal phenomenon in fullerene/donor molecule complexes²⁵. Solvent dependent photo physical behavior is a typical phenomenon of the most fullerene/porphyrin dyads studied to date²⁶. Photo physical studies already proves that in conformationally flexible fullerene/porphyrin dyad, π -stacking interactions facilitate the through space interactions between these two chromophores which is demonstrated by quenching of fluorescence intensity and formation of fullerene excited states (by energy transfer) or generation of fullerene⁻/porphyrin⁺ ion-pair states (by electron transfer). However, in non-polar solvent, energy transfer generally dominates (over the electron transfer process) the photo physical behavior in deactivating the photo excited chromophore

Table 1. Binding constants (K), selectivity in K , i.e. $K_{C_{70}}/K_{C_{60}}$, heat of formation value (ΔH_f^0), surface area (A) and volume (V) of the fullerene/1 complexes at 298 K temperature

	K ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)		Selectivity ($K_{C_{70}}/K_{C_{60}}$)		ΔH_f^0 (kcal mol^{-1})	A (\AA^2)	V (\AA^3)	R_s (eV)
	UV-Vis	Fluores.	UV-Vis	Fluores.				
$C_{60}/1$	18340	4570	1.7	3.3	-19.21	1066 84	1235.94	-0.64
$C_{70}/1$	31700	15000			-66.68	1082 24	1305 43	-0.69

Fig. 5. (a) Fluorescence quenching of 1 ($3.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) by C_{60} (from (i) $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to (viii) $1.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in toluene medium; inset of Fig. 5(a) depicts plot of relative fluorescence intensity vs $[C_{60}]$ for the $C_{60}/1$ system at 298 K; (b) BH fluorescence plot of $C_{60}/1$ system in toluene at 298 K.

1^* porphyrin of fullerene/porphyrin non-covalent complex. The spectral changes finally reach a plateau, indicating

that the fluorescence quenching is induced by the complexation. The binding constants are evaluated according

Fig. 4S. (a) Fluorescence quenching of **1** ($3.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) by C_{70} (from (i) $3.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to (ix) $3.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in toluene medium; inset of above figure depicts plot of relative fluorescence intensity vs $[C_{60}]$ for the $C_{70}/\mathbf{1}$ system at 298 K; (b) BH fluorescence plot of $C_{70}/\mathbf{1}$ system in toluene at 298 K.

to a modified BH equation of following type (eq. (2)) :

$$F_0/(F_0 - F) = (1/A) + \{(1/KA) (1/[\text{fullerene}])\} \quad (2)$$

In eq. (2), F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensity of porphyrin without and with the fullerenes, respectively, $[\text{fullerene}]$ the molar concentration of fullerene; and A is the constant associated with the difference in the emission quantum yield of the complexed and uncomplexed porphyrin. By plotting $F_0/(F_0 - F)$ versus $1/([\text{fullerene}])$, excellent linear plots have been obtained for both the $C_{60}/$ - and $C_{70}/$ - complexes of **1** (Figs. 5(b) and 4S(b), respectively). Values of K determined by fluorescence method are given in Table 1. Trend in the K values for

the fullerene/**1** complexes suggests that tight fixation of C_{70} takes place in the well defined structure of **1** giving rise to correct host-guest orientation. It is, however, observed that the K values determined by fluorescence method are somewhat lower in magnitude with those obtained from the UV-Vis absorption studies.

Time-resolved fluorescence studies :

The time-resolved fluorescence spectral features of the fullerene/**1** systems track the steady state measurements. The fluorescence decay-time profiles of the investigated complexes of **1** (monitored at 405 nm using 462 nm LASER diode) shows an enhanced decay rate as compared to uncomplexed **1**. In toluene, all of the investigated species, viz. **1**, $C_{60}/\mathbf{1}$ and $C_{70}/\mathbf{1}$, reveal biexponential decay. Substantial quenching of the fluorescence lifetime is observed for the investigated dyads; the $C_{70}/\mathbf{1}$ system clearly shows a higher efficiency of quenching than that of $C_{60}/\mathbf{1}$ system (Fig. 6). While the insufficient polarity of toluene prevents an appreciable stabilization of the radical

Fig. 6. Time resolved fluorescence spectrum of **1** ($8.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in (a) absence and presence of (b) C_{60} ($2.33 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and (c) C_{70} ($2.57 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

pair, we may assume that the quenching is due to energy transfer from the singlet excited state of porphyrin to fullerene. In our present investigations, we have determined the rates of charge separation (k_{CS}^{singlet}) and quantum yields ($\phi_{CS}^{\text{singlet}}$) in an usual manner employed for the intermolecular energy and/electron-transfer process and the data are provided in Table 2. An examination of Table 2 reveals that the experimentally determined values of k_{CS}^{singlet} and $\phi_{CS}^{\text{singlet}}$ are found to be higher for $C_{70}/\mathbf{1}$ complex as compared to the $C_{60}/\mathbf{1}$ complex. This

Table 2. Fluorescence lifetimes (τ_f), charge separation rate constant at singlet state ($k_{CS}^{singlet}$) and charge separation quantum yield at singlet state ($\phi_{CS}^{singlet}$) for the designed zinc porphyrin 1 in absence and presence of C_{60} and C_{70} . Temp. 298 K

	τ_f		$10^9 k_{CS}^{singlet}$		$\phi_{CS}^{singlet}$		
	(ns)		$(s^{-1})^a$		b		
Blank	$C_{60}/1$	$C_{70}/1$	$C_{60}/1$	$C_{70}/1$	$C_{60}/1$	$C_{70}/1$	
	0.062	0.059	0.034	0.830	13.30	0.050	0.452

$k_{CS}^{singlet} = (1/\tau_f)_{sample} - (1/\tau_f)_{ref}$, $\phi_{CS}^{singlet} = [(1/\tau_f)_{sample} - (1/\tau_f)_{ref}]/(1/\tau_f)_{sample}$

observation is consistent with the close proximity of the monoporphyrin molecule 1 and fullerene entity in the $C_{70}/1$ complex as obtained from the magnitude of K value of such complex. Secondly, in agreement with the steady state emission results, time-resolved fluorescence experiment suggests that with the increasing value of electron affinity of the acceptor (here C_{70}), both the values of $k_{CS}^{singlet}$ and $\phi_{CS}^{singlet}$ increase, remarkably.

Theoretical calculations :

The large size of the fullerene/monoporphyrin system limits the use of density functional theory or Hartree-Fock (HF) calculations for the determination of accurate quantum-mechanical electronic structure and association energies for these types of systems. For this reason, we adopt less expensive and time-consuming calculations in order to get an overview of the molecular picture *in vacuo* that will perhaps illuminate the actual solution phase interactions for these supramolecular systems. However, it is well established that semiempirical and minimal basis set *ab initio* (HF) calculations do not reproduce the close approach between these two chromophoric moieties. This is an expected result if van der Waals interactions play dominant role as these sorts of calculations do not take into account electron correlation effect. In this circumstance, it is desirable to employ MMMF calculations to reproduce the above features. The heat of formation values (ΔH_f^0) together with the surface area and volumes for the $C_{60}/1$ and $C_{70}/1$ systems have been calculated in the present investigations and respective data are given in Table 1. Stereoscopic structures for all the fullerene/1 complexes are visualized in Fig. 7. These results demonstrate that interaction between C_{70} and 1 is favoured over C_{60} and 1 in a comprehensive manner. Such motif of C_{70} towards 1 is considered to be originated due to the greater π - π contact area of the porphyrin with the equatorial region of C_{70} ²⁷. Thus, in the case of $C_{70}/1$ complex, the

Fig. 7. MMMF optimized stereoscopic structures of (a) $C_{60}/1$ and (b) $C_{70}/1$ systems done *in vacuo*.

side-on interaction of C_{70} with 1 generates ΔH_f^0 value of $-66.68 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, whereas ΔH_f^0 is determined to be $-19.21 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ in case of $C_{60}/1$ complex. Thus, $C_{70}/1$ complex gains $\sim 47.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ of extra stabilization energy when it approaches the cavity of 1. It should be mentioned that we have tried to estimate the ΔH_f^0 value of $C_{70}/1$ complex when C_{70} approaches the cavity of 1 in its end-on orientation. However, we fail to do so as the resulting geometry adopts the stable side-on pattern. This is because the discrimination between the two orientations of C_{70} towards complexation with 1 is energetically more pronounced in case of the metallo-porphyrin receptor, i.e. 1²⁸. In our present investigations, we have also

measured the surface area (A) and volume (V) of the fullerene/1 complexes using the MMMF calculations. The greater amount of A and V for the $C_{70}/1$ complex in comparison to $C_{60}/1$ complex (Table 2) also proves that the interaction between C_{70} and 1 is favoured very much. The higher ΔH_f^0 value as we observe for $C_{70}/1$ system in comparison to $C_{60}/1$, may also be rationalized by the fact that desolvation of the fullerenes take place at a much lesser extent with smaller C_{60} molecule than that of C_{70} . This is due to the fact that the solubility of C_{60} (4.1 mg/mL) is found to be two times higher compared to C_{70} (2.0 mg/mL) in toluene medium²⁹. It is already well established that the 6 : 6 ring-juncture bond of the C_{70} , rather than 6 : 5 ring-juncture bond, lies closest to the porphyrin plane as the 6 : 6 "double" bonds of C_{70} are found to be more electron-rich than 6 : 5 "single" bonds. Thus, the equatorial face of C_{70} is centered over the electropositive centre of the porphyrin plane which may be viewed as an artificial enhancement in van der Waals interaction due to availability of greater surface area favouring strong π - π interactions. The fundamentally strong π - π interaction is, therefore, augmented by weak electrostatic or donor acceptor stabilization. This is the second component of fullerene/porphyrin interaction motif. The frequently observed alignment of a fullerene 6 : 6 ring-juncture "double" bond with a *trans* N.....N vector has been rationalized on electrostatic grounds³⁰. The electron-rich porphyrin N atoms are positioned over regions of positive electrostatic potential near the centres of the fullerene rings. This is consistent with the prevailing view of porphyrin dimers where dispersion forces create the fundamental attraction and weaker electrostatic forces control the mutual orientation. The interaction can also be rationalized according to Hunter and Sanders' view of π - π complex where the detailed geometry of intermolecular interactions is determined by the properties of the atoms at the points of intermolecular contact (mainly electrostatic attraction/repulsion) rather than overall molecular properties³¹. It is primarily controlled by the strong dispersion forces that bring them in close proximity (inside the van der Waals contact distance), but perhaps the detailed local alignment is then determined by the local electrostatics, proposed earlier³⁰. Previous studies on the role of metalation of porphyrin in controlling the binding with fullerene have shown somewhat variable trends³².

As far as binding of fullerenes to porphyrins is concerned (Table 2), the affinities of metalloporphyrins towards fullerenes do not follow a regular trend when compared with that of the corresponding free base analogue^{33,34}. This is indeed a very general observation in fullerene/porphyrin systems although it is clear that a number of small effects conspire to affect the value of K in different ways that do not always lend themselves to easy deconvolution.

Although, the present selectivity ratio i.e. $K_{C_{70}}/K_{C_{60}}$ ~ 2.5 , is found to be comparable with those of azacalix[*m*]arene[*n*]pyridine (~ 1.9)³⁵ and cyclotrimeratrylenophane (~ 2.5)³⁶ hosts, it is shown to exhibit much lower value than those observed for carbon nanoring (~ 16)³⁷, cyclic dimers of Zn-porphyrins (~ 25.5)³⁸ and H_2 -diporphyrin (~ 32)³⁹.

Solvent reorganization energy (R_S) :

The effect of solvent over electronic coupling between a host and a guest is likely to be important in the present systems. For this reason, solvent reorganization energies (R_S) are calculated for the fullerene complexes of 1. The total reorganization energy, R_S , is a sum of the two terms, i.e. inner-sphere reorganization energy (solvent-independent) R_0 , and outer-sphere reorganization energy (solvent-dependent) R_S . In case of fullerene, contributions from R_0 , which is related to the differences in nuclear configurations between an initial and a final state, are very small, $\sim 4.3 \times 10^{-5}$ eV⁴⁰. This observation implies that the structure of C_{60} and C_{70} in the ground and excited states is very similar, which relates to the rigidity of these spherical carbon structures. As far as R_S contribution is concerned, this is also believed to be small as well. Thus the symmetrical shape and large size of the fullerene framework requires little energy for the adjustment of an excited or reduced state to the new solvent environment. In the present investigation R_S of $C_{60}/1$ and $C_{70}/1$ complexes have been estimated applying the dielectric continuum model developed by Hauke *et al.*⁴¹. Values of R_S for the $C_{60}/1$ and $C_{70}/1$ systems are given in Table 2. It is to be mentioned that solvent reorganization energies obtained in the present investigation do not corroborate well with that observed for porphyrin/quinone system⁴⁰. The discrepancy in the value of R_S for porphyrin/quinone and fullerene/porphyrin systems may be due

to the subtle structural change in the host-guest complex which exert a large influence upon the photo induced electron and energy transfer process.

Conclusions :

From the foregoing discussions we can summarize the results of the following investigations as follows :

(1) Ground state non-covalent interactions between fullerenes (C₆₀ and C₇₀) and a octaethyl Zn^{II} porphyrin namely, **1**, has been established in toluene medium by both absorption spectrophotometric and steady state fluorescence measurements.

(2) Estimation of binding constants reveal that **1** may not selectively be employed as molecular tweezers for C₇₀.

(3) The higher value binding constant for the C₇₀/1 complex is indicative of more favorable interaction between C₇₀ and **1**.

(4) Time resolved fluorescence measurements establish efficient charge-separation for the fullerene/1 complexes. Order of *k*_{CS} value establishes that energy transfer takes place from the excited singlet state of porphyrin to the fullerene in toluene medium.

(6) Heat of formation value estimated by MMMF calculations *in vacuo* indicates side-on interaction motif of C₇₀ with the π-belt of **1**.

(7) Higher negative value of *R*_S for the C₇₀/1 system than that of C₆₀/1 proves that the former complex is stabilized more in terms of solvent reorganization energy.

(8) The results emanating from present the investigations explore the possibility of employing this particular zinc porphyrin as a suitable building block for derivatized fullerenes in near future.

Supporting information available :

UV-Vis titration experiment of **1** in presence of C₇₀, Jobs plot of C₆₀/1 system, BH plot of C₇₀/1 system, steady state fluorescence titration experiment of **1** in presence of C₇₀ along with fluorescence induced curve and BH fluorescence of such system in toluene are provided as Figs. 1S-4S, respectively.

Acknowledgement

PM thanks to The Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University, to carry out his research work by providing

him infrastructural facilities. SB wishes to record his gratitude to UGC, New Delhi for providing financial support to him through the project of F. No. 34-336/2008 (SR).

References

1. N. Aratani, A. Osuka, Y. H. Kim, D. H. Jeong and D. Kim, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 1458.
2. B. Szczsna and Z. U. Lipkowska, *New. J. Chem.*, 2002, **26**, 243.
3. M. M. Olmstead, D. A. Costa, K. Maitra, B. C. Noll, S. L. Phillips, P. M. Van Calcar and A. L. Balch, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 7090.
4. L. Flamigni, F. Barigelletti, N. Armaroli, J. P. Collin, I. M. Dixon, J. P. Sauvage and J. A. G. Williams, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **190**, 671.
5. Z. M. Lin, W. Z. Feng and H. K. Leung, *Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 209.
6. M. E. El-Khouly, Y. Araki, O. Ito, S. Gadde, A. L. McCarty, P. A. Karr, M. E. Zandler and F. D'Souza, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2005, **7**, 2006.
7. T. J. Kesti, N. V. Tkachenko, V. Vehmanen, H. Yamada, H. Imahori, S. Fukuzumi and H. Lemmetyinen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 8067.
8. F. D'Souza and O. Ito, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 4913.
9. "Encyclopedia of Supramolecular Chemistry", eds. J. L. Atwood, J. W. Steed and M. Dekker, 2004, Vol. 2.
10. H. Spillmann, A. Kiebele, M. Stöhr, T. A. Jung, D. Bonifazi, F. Y. Cheng and F. Diederich, *Adv. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 275.
11. M. D. Meizer, G. P. M. V. Klink and G. V. Koten, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **230**, 141.
12. "The Chemistry of Fullerenes", ed. R. Taylor, World Scientific, Singapore, 1995.
13. Y. Sun, T. Drovetskaya, R. D. Bolskar, R. Bau, P. W. D. Boyd and C. A. Reed, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1997, **62**, 3642.
14. L. J. Prins, D. N. Reinhoudt and P. Timmerman, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 2383.
15. N. V. Tkachenko, C. Guenther, H. Imahori, Y. Tamaki Sakata, S. Fukuzumi and H. Lemmetyinen, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2000, **326**, 344.
16. V. Vehmanen, N. V. Tkachenko, H. Imahori, S. Fukuzumi and H. Lemmetyinen, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2001, **57**, 2229.
17. N. Armaroli, G. Marconi, L. Echegoyen, J. P. Bourgeois and F. Diederich, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2000, **6**, 1629.
18. P. Mukherjee, S. K. Nayak, S. Banerjee (Bhattacharya), S. Chattopadhyay and S. Bhattacharya, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2008, **889**, 352.

- 19 S Bhattacharya, S K Nayak, S Chattopadhyay and M Banerjee, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 2007, **68**, 495
- 20 S Bhattacharya, N Ujihashi, S Aonuma, T Kimura and N Komatsu, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 2007, **68**, 495
- 21 M Gouterman, G H Wagniere and L C Synder, *J Mol Spectros* , 1963, **11** 108
- 22 D M Guidi, T D Ros, P Braiuca and M Prato, *Photochem Photobiol Sci* , 2003, **2**, 1067
- 23 H A Benesi and J H Hildebrand, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1949, **71**, 2703
- 24 I B Martini, B Ma, T Da Ros, R Helgeson F Wudl and B J Schwartz, *Chem Phys Lett* , 2000, **327**, 253 and the references cited there in
- 25 D I Schuster, P Cheng, S R Wilson, V Prokhorenko, M Katterle, A R Holzwarth, S E Braslavsky, G Klihm, R M Williams and C Luo, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1999, **121**, 11599
- 26 D I Schuster, P Cheng, S R Wilson, V Prokhorenko, M Katterle, A R Holzwarth, S E Braslavsky, G Klihm, R M Williams and C Luo, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1999, **121**, 11599
- 27 P D W Boyd, M C Hodgson, C E F Rickard, A G Oliver, L Chaker, P J Brothers, R D Bolskar, F S Tham and C A Reed, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1999, **121**, 10487
- 28 S Bhattacharya, K Tominaga, T Kimura, H Uno and N Komatsu, *Chem Phys Lett* , 2007, **433**, 395
- 29 X Zhou *et al* , *Carbon*, 1994, **32**, 935
- 30 Y -B Wang and Z Lin, *J Am Chem Soc* , 2003 **125**, 6072
- 31 C A Hunter and J K M Sanders, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1990, **112**, 5525
- 32 P D W Boyd and C A Reed, *Acc Chem Res* 2005, **38**, 235
- 33 J -Y Zheng, K Tashiro, Y Hirabayashi, K Kinbara, K Saigo, T Aida, S Sakamoto and K Yamaguchi *Angew Chem , Int Ed* , 2001, **40**, 1858
- 34 M Dudic, P Lhotak, I Stibor, H Petricková and K Lang, *New J Chem* , 2004, **28**, 85
- 35 M -X Wang, X -H Zhang and Q -Yo Zheng, *Angew Chem , Int Ed* , 2004, **43**, 838
- 36 H Matsubara, S Oguri, K Asano and K Yamamoto *Chem Lett* , 1999, 431
- 37 T Kawase, K Tanaka, Y Seirai N Shino and M Oda, *Angew Chem , Int Ed* , 2003, **42**, 5597
- 38 Y Shoji, K Tashiro and T Aida, *J Am Chem Soc* 2004 **126** 6570
- 39 D I Schuster, P D Jarowski A N Kirschner and S R Wilson, *J Mater Chem* , 2002, **12** 2041
- 40 D M Guidi and N Martin (eds), "Fullerenes From Synthesis to Optoelectronic Applications", Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, 2002
- 41 F Hauke, A Hirsch, S G Liu, L Echegoyen A Swartz, C Luo and D M Guidi, *Chem Phys Chem* 2002, **3**, 195